

Self-Management Skills and Work Commitment of Teachers in Occidental District, Digos City

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the extent of self-management skills as a determinant of the work commitment of teachers in Occidental District, Digos City Division. The findings revealed that self-management in terms of curriculum, planning and assessment, teaching all students, family and community engagement, and professional culture were oftentimes manifested. However, teachers presented the lessons in the easiest ways; asking questions that were easy to answer and giving quizzes to measure understanding of the lesson were sometimes manifested. However, in the professional culture of schools, teachers should exert more effort to create a positive learning environment for the children. Teachers showed difficulty providing all learners with a safe learning environment and learning resources and materials. Moreover, the work commitment of teachers in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment were extensive. However, teachers were not easily deterred by difficulties or setbacks. Teachers' encouragement to think positively was sometimes manifested. manifested, which was consistently striving to meet targets and objectives and having a strong sense of what I want to achieve from my jobs and career. There was a significant relationship between self-management skills and the work commitment of teachers. Teachers' self-management skills in curriculum, planning and assessment, teaching all students, family and community engagement, and professional culture significantly influence their work commitment.

KEY WORDS

1. self-management skills 2. work commitment 3. continuance commitment

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1. Introduction

Self-management skills encompass a range of abilities such as time management, organization, goal-setting, and stress management. These skills are essential for teachers to effectively handle the demands of their roles, including lesson planning, grading, communication with students and parents, and professional development activities. However, challenges may arise when teachers struggle to balance competing demands, leading to stress, burnout, and reduced job satisfaction. On the other hand, work commitment relates to the level of dedication, loyalty, and engagement teachers have toward their work and their students. High levels of work commitment are associated with increased job performance, job satisfaction, and retention rates. However, workload, administrative support, compensation, and recogni-

tion can influence teachers' commitment levels. When teachers feel overwhelmed or undervalued, their commitment to their work may diminish, leading to decreased motivation and morale and, ultimately, a negative impact on student learning outcomes for career advancement can help foster more outstanding work commitment among educators. In the Global context, Taiwan grappled with significant issues concerning teachers' self-management skills and work commitment, which played pivotal roles in shaping the quality of education. Scholars such as Chen and Lin (2019) underscored the importance of addressing these issues to enhance teacher effectiveness and job satisfaction. However, challenges such as heavy workloads, administrative pressures, and insufficient support systems often strain teachers' abilities to maintain effective self-management strategies. Wang and Chang (2019) highlighted the adverse effects of reduced work commitment, including increased teacher turnover, decreased morale, and diminished instructional quality. These issues not only impacted teachers' well-being and job satisfaction but also had significant implications for student learning outcomes. To mitigate these challenges, it was imperative to implement strategies aimed at revitalizing teacher commitment and enhancing job satisfaction. Vietnam faced considerable hurdles regarding teacher labor dedication, which is an essential element in determining the country's educational quality. Scholars such as Nguyen and Tran (2020) stressed the critical necessity of addressing these challenges to improve teacher effectiveness and overall educational performance. Work commitment among instructors includes dedication, motivation, and engagement in their careers, all required to create a conducive learning environment and promote student achievement. However, various problems, including burdensome workloads, low incomes, restricted professional development opportunities, and insufficient support systems, frequently contributed to decreased work commitment among educators. These concerns greatly impacted student learning results, instructors' well-being, and job satisfaction. To address these issues, it was critical to deploy initiatives to revive teacher dedication and increase job satisfaction. This could include measures like competitive compensation and benefits, chances for ongoing professional development, supportive work cultures, and recognizing and honoring teachers' achievements. Le and Pham (2020) According to the Malaysia Education Blueprint (2013-2025), the Ministry of Education has set a target of 92 This is due to high self-efficacy teachers being more enthusiastic and highly committed to organizational planning and willing to deal with self-efficacy, which is very important for students' behavior (Zhang et al., 2020). This also proves to be improved because it can influence teachers' feelings, thoughts, and behaviors while performing their responsibilities to educate and shape the personality of students (Agbaria, 2021; Zhang et al., 2020). Highly committed teachers are considered an asset in any school. Thus, commitment has become an important aspect to be developed and nurtured among school teachers (Cheng Gan, 2020) In the Philippines, teachers' poor work commitment is evident in the low attendance of teachers at parent-teacher conferences, delayed submission of reports like that of class nutritional status, and failure to distribute students' report cards on the scheduled date. Public school teachers' workload is limited to teaching and other non-teaching tasks (David et al., 2019). Additionally, teachers are expected to perform numerous duties at a high level and consider various factors in managing their students' learning (Erdogan Cavl, 2019). Every public school states that school teachers must engage in at least 6 hours of actual classroom teaching and equivalent teaching-related activities to complete the 8-hour workday, and 2 hours of work inside or outside the school premises are carried out in teaching-related ac-

tivities (Agpay, 2019). With this issue, there is a discontinuity of reactions about teachers experiencing high-stress levels, exhaustion, and low morale while performing work (Llego, 2019). Certain teachers refrain from conducting home visits to students who are at risk of dropping out. School administrators are concerned about the potential consequences of these teachers' neglect, as it could lead to future challenges for all stakeholders involved. In the local setting, at the time of the study, the Schools Division Superintendent of Digos City Division urged school heads during the Management Committee meeting to immediately address the issue of teacher's delayed submission of the school reports as some teachers are not able to accomplish on time school reports on reading inventory, monthly student's attendance report, and minutes of the conducted home-room meetings. The outcomes of this study and the beneficiaries of its findings. Public School District Supervisors stand to benefit from the findings as they can utilize them to design programs aimed at

enhancing teaching and learning processes. By offering appropriate technical assistance and implementing effective mechanisms for monitoring school programs, supervisors can contribute to improved school performance. School Heads can also leverage the study's results to plan for curriculum delivery improvements and prioritize the welfare of learners. By providing teachers with targeted technical support based on the study's findings, school heads can work towards achieving high learner outcomes. For teachers themselves, the study's results provide valuable insights into the factors influencing learner outcomes, reinforcing their crucial role as frontline educators. Additionally, learners benefit from the study's findings by receiving appropriate interventions tailored to the new everyday educational landscape. Furthermore, the study serves as a valuable resource for future researchers, offering a rich source of data and serving as a foundation for further investigation in the field of education.

2. Methodology

This presented the methods used in the study, which consisted of the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of self-management skills and work commitment on Occidental District, Digos City Division.

2.1. Research Design—The researcher employed the non-experimental quantitative design utilizing the descriptive method of research by which the main tool was the adapted and modified standardized survey questionnaire to determine the significant relationship between self-management skills and work commitment. As per Calmorin (1995), as referenced in Changiz, et al. (2020), a descriptive survey was employed when the research aims to obtain a detailed understanding of the population being studied, including their social and economic attributes, opinions, and their level of

understanding or behavior regarding a particular phenomenon. In this study, the researcher employed quantitative descriptive research using the correlation analysis method. Descriptive research is a type of quantitative research that involves careful descriptions of educational phenomena. This research design has limited control over extraneous variables, no manipulation of the independent variable, and was susceptible to threats and internal validity. Quantitative research was a formal, objective, systematic process in which numerical data were used to obtain information about the world.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—The respondents of the study were (45) out of 230 teachers of Occidental District, Digos City Division who have been in the service for three (3) years and are deemed to be permanent employees, who were randomly selected. The sample size was obtained using the fishbowl technique. In this technique, the researcher was randomly picked out from the fishbowl of all teachers in their respective schools. These employees were considered the respondents of the study.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The researcher utilized adapted questionnaires from the studies of Ganser T. (2018) and Hsiao et al. (2019), which were modified to suit the concept, place, situation, and ideas of the present study. The draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions, and recommendations. The final copy of the research survey questionnaire was validated by the panel of experts for approval. The final revision was made by incorporating all the corrections, comments, and suggestions given by the experts before distribution and administration. The draft of the questionnaire was presented and evaluated by some expert validators. A standard evaluation tool was provided to them to rate, comment, and suggestions for the improvement and development of the questionnaire. The results of the validation, together with the draft

of the research instrument, were submitted to the research adviser for comments and suggestions. The ambiguous items were deleted; the weak items were strengthened and improved. After correction and refinement, the research instrument was returned to the researcher for finalization. The pilot testing was conducted in Occidental District, Digos City and the respondents were not included in the research survey. The pilot testing was purposely conducted to establish the reliability and validity of the test instrument. The Cronbach alpha score is higher than 0.7, indicating good consistency among the item variables. The questionnaire was designed and modified to suit the needs of the respondents. This study used adapted and modified questionnaires. The first set was designed to gather information concerning the extent of self-management skills in terms of curriculum, planning, and assessment, teaching all students, family and community engagement, and professional culture. The second set is designed to gather data on work commitment in terms of affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment in Occidental District, Digos City Division. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of self-management skills. The five-point Likert scale was used in this study to describe the extent of work commitment. The following interpretations of the data are found below:

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation

Scale Rating	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The self-management skills are always manifested.
3.41 – 4.20	Extensive	The self-management skills are oftentimes manifested.
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Extensive	Self-management skills are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.60	Less Extensive	The self-management skills approach is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The self-management skills approach is not manifested.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation

Scale Rating	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The work commitment is always manifested.
3.41 – 4.20	Extensive	The work commitment is oftentimes manifested.
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Extensive	The work commitment is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.60	Less Extensive	The work commitment is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The work commitment is not manifested.

The researcher followed the following procedures in this study. Permission to conduct the study. The necessary data were gathered through the following procedure: The researcher asked permission from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Digos City Division to conduct an online survey of the teachers of Occidental District. Likewise, the granted letter of permission from the Schools Division Superintendent was brought to the principals and supervisors of public schools in Occidental District for the arrangement of the conduct of the research study. On the other hand, the researcher observed and followed strict compliance of the AITF or Inter-Agency Task Force for managing emerging infectious diseases in the process and conduct of the study. The arrangement was made with the school principals and supervisors upon observation of safety protocol regarding the conduct of the research. Distribution and retrieval of the survey questionnaire. On November 18, 2023, the graduate

student received an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School for the division superintendent’s approval. On November 25, 2023, a letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the School Principal, and the concerned gender and development coordinators was prepared for accessible data collection. Upon approval, the researcher personally administered the research, conducted the survey, and retrieved the data through an online platform. The survey questionnaire was sent through the respondents’ email, and once answered, it was sent to the researcher’s email. A received copy of the letter presented was secured by the principals to vouch that the researcher had honestly conducted and collected the data from the study participants online. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The data gathered was tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted confidentially accordingly. The study’s results were analyzed and interpreted based on its purpose.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used, and the null hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 significance level. The data were gathered, tallied, and treated using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences. Mean. The weighted arithmetic mean applies to options of different weights (Calmorin, 1998). This statistical tool was used in this study to measure the extent of self-management skills and work commitment. Pearson’s r. The person product-

moment of the correlation coefficient was a linear correlation used to find the degree of the association between two sets of variables (Calmorin, 1998). This statistical tool was used in this study to determine the significant relationship between self-management skills and work commitment in Occidental District, Digos City Division. Regression Analysis. The regression analysis was used to determine the domains of self-management skills that significantly influence teachers’ work commitment.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the problems in this study. They are thoroughly discussed, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Self-management skills and work commitment of teachers.

Summary of the Extent of self-management skills Table 1 presents the summary of the Extent of self-management skills in terms of its indicators, namely Curriculum, Planning, Assessment, Pedagogy, Family and Community Engagement, and Professional Culture among teachers in public elementary schools. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Family and Community Engagement (4.30), and Professional Culture (4.19). The overall mean rating of 4.26 suggests that self-management skills are always manifested, thus very extensive among teachers in public elementary schools. The results depicted in Table 5 were

supported by the idea of Kelty Wakabayashi (2020) pointed out that by valuing the insights provided by families regarding their children’s interests and challenges, we can adapt teaching methods to better suit individual learning needs, thereby enhancing the overall learning experience. Additionally, integrating elements of students’ home cultures into classroom teachings, as suggested by Hong (2019), fosters a more inclusive and culturally responsive learning environment. Family engagement leading to enriched social experiences is a significant predictor of children’s cognitive skills, and social-emotional skills, including motivation, attention, impulse control, and self-confidence.

Table 1. Summary on Extent of Self-management Skills

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Curriculum, Planning, and Assessment	4.27	Very Extensive
2	Pedagogy	4.29	Very Extensive
3	Family and Community Engagement	4.30	Very Extensive
4	Professional Culture	4.19	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.26	Very Extensive

The researcher highlights the critical role of family engagement in shaping children’s cognitive and social-emotional development. By actively involving families in the educational process and valuing their insights, educators can tailor teaching methods to better address individual learning needs, thus enhancing the overall learning experience for students. Additionally, integrating elements of students’ home cultures into classroom teachings fosters inclusivity and cultural responsiveness, creating a more enriching learning environment. In ad-

dition, self-management strategies can save organizations time and money and increase the efficiency of work carried out by employees. The presence of self-management strategies increases task performance, innovation, and creativity of employees, which increases employees’ engagement and ultimately productivity in the workplace (Ghali, Habeeb, Hamzah, 2018). Appropriate self-management can help students perform better in school, can reduce delinquent behaviors, and can help individuals perform better on the job. For example, an inappropriate

display of anger (like shouting at or threatening a teacher or a boss) may cause an individual to be punished by removal from the classroom or place of employment. Further escalated displays of anger can result in punching or kicking objects or people, which may result in charges of battery or damage to property.

Summary of the Extent of Work Commitment Table 2 summarizes the extent of teachers' work commitment in terms of affective, contin-

uance, and normative commitment. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: affective commitment (4.30), normative commitment (4.30), and continuance commitment (4.27) are always manifested. The overall mean rating of 4.28 suggests that teacher commitment to work is always manifested, thus very extensive, among teachers.

Table 2. Summary on Extent of Work Commitment of Teachers

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Affective Commitment	4.30	Very Extensive
2	Continuance Commitment	4.27	Very Extensive
3	Normative Commitment	4.30	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.29	Very Extensive

Teacher commitment was the emotional bond teachers demonstrate toward their work. It has been recognized as one of the most critical factors in effective teaching. Teachers with a high level of commitment could make a difference in their students' learning and achievement. Competence and commitment are equally important to being a good teacher. One can have all the passion in the world, but without competence and the ability to teach, one cannot become an excellent teacher.

Significant Relationship between self-management skills and work commitment of teachers

Affective commitment is also called attitudinal commitment. Khan et al. (2019) believed that commitment exceeds utilitarian values, which is consistent with organizational values as an affective orientation. However, Haider et al. (2019) believe that affective commitment is the employees' dependence on the organization under emotional belonging, which is the same as the organizational goals and values. Therefore, it is more lasting than the material

transaction relationship (Haider et al., 2019). This researcher's perspective emphasizes that affective commitment extends beyond mere utilitarian values, suggesting that it encompasses a deeper alignment with organizational values and goals. This viewpoint underscores the emotional orientation of commitment, suggesting that individuals who are effectively committed to an organization are driven by a sense of attachment, loyalty, and identification with its mission and culture. This form of commitment transcends transactional relationships and is characterized by a lasting emotional bond that motivates individuals to go above and beyond in their contributions to the organization. Continuance commitment is considered as an individual's desire to advance the organization because of consideration of sacrifices and losses that must be paid if it leaves the organization. Continuance commitment shows that commitment is based on workers' losses if they leave the organization. Continuance Commitment is based on employee perceptions of the losses that will be obtained if he does not continue

his work in a company. In other words, the employee is still working for a company because he requires salary and other benefits or because he has not found another job. Continuance commitment is measured by several indicators (Busro, 2018) including. Profits when continuing to work in the organization. Losses when leaving the organization. The notion that continuance commitment is driven by considerations of sacrifices and losses highlights the role of perceived costs in shaping individuals' commitment to their organization. Employees may feel a sense of obligation to remain with the organization due to the potential negative consequences, such as financial loss or decreased benefits, associated with leaving. This perspective suggests that continuance commitment is not solely motivated by positive aspects of the employment relationship, but also by the desire to avoid potential drawbacks or hardships that may arise from discontinuing employment. According to Dwiyanete et al., (2022), normative commitment is defined as a sense of obligation for an individual to remain in the organization. This normative commitment is a form of obligation that must be carried out by a worker for his organization. Employees who are strongly committed to this normative commitment will tend to stay and remain in the organization because of the feeling of having to stay in the organization. Moreover, the notion that normative commitment involves a feeling of "having to stay" highlights the involuntary nature of this commitment. Unlike continuance commitment,

A study by Baek, Kang, and Shin (2019) examined the relationship between self-management skills and job satisfaction among teachers in South Korea. Although not directly focused on work commitment, the findings suggested that self-management skills, such as time management and goal setting, were positively associated with job satisfaction, which could

which may be driven by perceived costs and benefits, normative commitment is rooted in a sense of duty or obligation that transcends individual self-interest. Employees who are strongly committed to this form of commitment are motivated by a sense of moral obligation to fulfill their responsibilities and contribute to the organization's goals and objectives. Significant Relationship Between Self-Management Skills and Work Commitment

Shown in Table 3 are data about the significant relationship between self-management skills and work commitment. Analyzing the data by Pearson Product –Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson r , the results are: the computed r -value for self-management skills versus work commitment of teachers is 0.62 which denotes an almost substantial relationship or definite relationship. While computing the significant difference of r –values, it is found as 4.41 with a probability value of 0.013, which is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there is a significant relationship between self-management skills and the work commitment of teachers. The greater the self-management skills the greater the work commitment, hence a positive correlation occurs when an increase in two variables decreases at the same time. This mere example of linear correlation or straight-line relationships between two variables. A correlation can range between -1 (perfect negative relationship) and +1 (perfect positive relationship), with 0 indicating no straight-line relationship.

potentially extend to work commitment. One insight derived from this study is the importance of self-management skills in enhancing job satisfaction among teachers. Effective time management and goal setting can help teachers prioritize tasks, meet deadlines, and achieve their professional objectives more efficiently. As a result, teachers may experience a greater

Table 3. The Significant Relationship between Self-management Skills and Work Commitment of Teachers

Variables	r-values	Computed t-value	P value	Remarks/Decision
Self-management skills (x) Work commitment (y)	0.62	4.41	0.013	Reject

Note: Significance when $P < 0.05$

sense of accomplishment and fulfillment in their roles, leading to higher levels of job satisfaction. Similarly, a study by Kim and Joo (2019) investigated the impact of self-regulated learning strategies on teacher commitment in the context of continuing professional development. While their focus was on self-regulated learning, which encompasses self-management skills, the study found a positive relationship between these strategies and teacher commitment. A significant finding from this research highlights a potential connection between the utilization of self-regulated learning techniques and the level of commitment displayed by teachers. Self-regulated learning encompasses a range of cognitive and metacognitive activities, including setting goals, organizing plans, monitoring progress, and reflecting on outcomes, all of which are fundamental aspects of effective self-management. On the indicators of self-management skills that significantly influence work commitment.

Table 4 depicts the regression coefficient analysis on the significant influence of self-management skills that significantly influence the work commitment of teachers in Digos,

Being the most important resource, organizations always acknowledge the worth of their employees and make considerable efforts to attract, retain, and maintain them in an organization (Aguiar-Quintana et al., 2020; Anggreyani et al., 2020). Commitment develops employees' interest, involvement, trust, and sense of owner-

ship of the organization where shared decisions are made devoid of discrimination between administration and employees (Andika Darmanto, 2020). Loan (2020) investigated that commitment strengthens the feelings to stay in an organization, which is related to the associated with all three types of commitment, such as af-

Occidental District. All indicators of self-management skills provided, namely curriculum, planning, and assessment (0.341), teaching all students (0.332), and family and community engagement (0.415), except professional culture (0.001), indicate statistically significant influence on work commitment of teachers in Digos City, Occidental District. This gives empirical evidence to show that the indicators of self-management skills provided directly influence work commitment. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.885 suggests that self-management skills account for 88.5 of the variance of work commitment. This provides empirical evidence that variability of the extent of self-management skills can be accounted for and be explained by the indicators as enumerated under the extent of work commitment among the teachers in Digos City, Occidental District. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (116.349) and p-statistic are significant $p_i.001$, which tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of work commitment teachers.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on the Implementation of Self-management Skills That Significantly Influence the Work Commitment of Teachers

Model	Unstandar-dized	Standard Error	Standar-dized	t	p	Decision
H (Intercept)	3.356	0.056		60.03	<.001	
H (Intercept)	0.167	0.157		1.069	0.287	
Curriculum, planning, and assessment	0.086	0.091	0.100	0.949	0.341	Accept Null
Teaching all students	0.132	0.092	0.158	1.444	0.332	Accept Null
Family and community engagement	0.203	0.082	0.257	2.472	0.001	Reject Null
Professional culture	0.337	0.073	0.425	4.638	<.415	Accept Null
R²	0.885					
F-value	116.349					
p-value	<.001					

fective continuance and normative commitment (Brooks et al., 2020). Effective teaching hinges on a deep sense of dedication. Without this commitment, even a thorough understanding of teaching theories loses its significance, and effective teaching remains out of reach. Through their dedication, teachers can fulfill their roles to the utmost, contributing to ongoing progress within the school community as they continually strive to excel in their profession. Creates some learning experiences that guide students to identify needs, ask for support, and challenge

themselves to take academic risks. Effectively models and reinforces ways that students can master challenging material through effective effort, rather than having to depend on innate ability. Consistently adapts instruction, materials, and assessments to make challenging material accessible to all students, including English learners and students with disabilities. To sum up, self-management skills contribute to the work commitment of teachers in Digos City, Occidental District.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and implications drawn. Findings were based on the problem’s posed statement; conclusions were based on the findings generated, and recommendations were based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following were the findings of the study given the results in the pre-

sentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of self-management skills in terms of its indica-

tors namely curriculum, planning, and assessment (4.27), pedagogy (4.29), family and community engagement (4.30), and professional culture (4.19) exhibits very extensive in its practice of self-management skills. The overall mean rating of 4.26 suggests the practice of self-management skills was always manifested, thus very extensive among elementary school teachers in Digos, Occidental District. The extent of the commitment to work in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment among schools in Digos, Occidental District, revealed that affective commitment (4.30), continuance commitment (4.27), and normative commitment (4.30) exhibits always manifested, thus being very extensive. The overall mean rating of 4.28 suggests that a commitment to work is always manifested among the teachers in Digos, Occidental District. Pearson's correlation showed a significant correlation between the extent of self-management skills ($r=0.745$; $p<.001$) and work commitment among teachers in Digos, Occidental District. All indicators of continuous improvement program provided, namely curriculum, planning, and assessment (0.341), teaching all students (0.332), and professional culture (0.415), except family and community engagement (0.001), indicate a statistically significant influence of work commitment among teachers in Digos, Oriental District.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the results presented, the following conclusions were drawn: The Extent of self-management skills in terms of curriculum, planning, and assessment, Pedagogy, Family and Community Engagement, and Professional Culture, was very extensive,

thus always manifested. The Extent of Work Commitment of Teachers in terms of affective commitment, Continuance commitment, and normative commitment was very extensive, thus always manifested. There was a relationship between self-management skills and work commitment. Results indicated sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there was a significant relationship between self-management skills and the work commitment of teachers.

4.3. Recommendations—This study focused on the relationship between self-management skills and work commitment. Public School District Supervisors. This study helped them design programs that helped teachers deliver effective teaching and learning processes. They can provide the appropriate technical assistance and proper mechanisms for monitoring school programs. The findings of this study served as the basis for planning, monitoring, and evaluating school performance. School Heads. The study helped them plan to improve curriculum delivery and the welfare of the learners. The school heads could use the results to provide technical assistance to teachers to ensure high learner outcomes. Teachers. The study's results helped teachers determine factors that affect learner outcomes. The findings served as a baseline to understand that teachers play a crucial role as the frontline in promoting learner outcomes in school. Learners. The beneficiary of this study helped learners receive appropriate intervention in the new normal. Future researchers. This study may serve as a valuable data source and as a basis for further study.

5. References

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